

Waste Classification and Segregation using Machine Learning

Keerthana Dinesh A

Department. of Computer Applications
Amal Jyothi College of Engineering
Kanjirappally, India
keerthanadinesha2023b@mca.ajce.in

Navyamol K T

Department. of Computer Applications
Amal Jyothi College of Engineering
Kanjirappally, India
navyamolkt@amaljyothi.ac.in

Abstract— Waste management is a key component of sustainable development, and Waste classification and recycling are essential to minimizing the harm that garbage causes to the environment. Recently, garbage classification jobs have showed considerable potential for computer vision algorithms. In this article, we provide a method that integrates knowledge of garbage recycling with classification using CNN's VGG16 Transfer Learning algorithm. The suggested method would let people categorise rubbish using their smartphones in an effort to raise awareness of waste recycling. The system utilises CNN's VGG16 Transfer Learning algorithm, which has been pre-trained on a sizable dataset of images and is a superb option for feature extraction. There are two phases to the system: training and testing. In the training stage, the VGG16 model is fine-tuned on a small dataset of waste images. In the testing stage, users can take a picture of the waste material using their smartphone, and the system classifies the waste material into one of the pre-defined categories.

Keywords—Waste recycling, Waste classification, Convolutional Neural Network, Transfer Learning, VGG16

I. INTRODUCTION

Globally, waste management raises serious environmental issues. The inappropriate disposal of waste can result in resource depletion, environmental contamination, and health risks. Recycling and sorting rubbish are essential for minimizing its harmful effects on the environment. Recycling entails repurposing waste materials into new goods while preserving natural resources and lowering the demand for virgin materials. Waste classification is the process of sorting waste materials into different categories based on their characteristics. In recent years, computer vision techniques have shown great promise in waste classification tasks. Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs) are a type of artificial neural network that has been widely used in image recognition and classification tasks.

CNNs are a great option for garbage classification tasks because they can automatically learn features from unprocessed visual data. In this article, we provide a method that integrates knowledge of garbage recycling with classification using CNN's VGG16 Transfer Learning algorithm. With the help of their web application, users of the proposed system would be able to classify waste products, raising awareness of waste recycling. The method the system employs for classification, VGG16 Transfer Learning, has

been pre-trained on a sizable dataset of images, making it a viable option for extracting features.

Training and testing are the two phases of the proposed system. The VGG16 model is modified during the training phase to recognize a small dataset of garbage images. Amid the testing stage, individuals can utilize their smartphones to require a photo of the garbage, and the framework will at that point classify the waste into one of the pre-determined categories. The framework may be a promising choice for applications including waste administration and reusing since of its effortless and comfort.

1. Convolutional neural network

Artificial neural networks known as CNNs, or convolutional neural networks, are often employed in computer vision applications including image recognition, segmentation, and object identification.

Convolutional, fully connected, and pooling layers are only a few of the many layers included in convolutional neural networks (CNNs). By using filters, convolutional layers are in charge of removing pertinent characteristics from incoming images. On the other side, pooling layers are utilized to reduce the derived features' spatial size. The final output is produced by classifying the extracted characteristics using fully linked layers.

A supervised learning technique is used to train CNNs, and during training, the network's neurons' weights are changed to teach it to recognize patterns in the input pictures. Using backpropagation, the error between the predicted output and the actual output is transmitted back through the network in order to iteratively update the weights of the neurons.

CNNs learn to recognize patterns in images by adjusting neuron weights through supervised learning. They can automatically learn features from raw image data, making them popular in computer vision tasks. CNNs have achieved state-of-the-art performance on benchmark datasets such as ImageNet, CIFAR-10, and MNIST.

CNNs have shown promise in waste classification by automatically categorizing waste materials based on their characteristics. A CNN that has been trained on a set of trash photographs may recognize patterns in those images and use those patterns to classify fresh garbage images. By making it

simpler to segregate garbage and prevent it from ending up in landfills, this can enhance waste management.

2. VGG16 Transfer Learning technique

The VGG16 architecture has been widely used for transfer learning in various computer vision tasks, including image classification. Transfer learning with VGG16 involves using the pre-trained weights of the network as a starting point for a new task, and then fine-tuning the network on a specific dataset to improve its accuracy and efficiency.

The University of Oxford's Visual Geometry Group created the 16-layer VGG16 architecture, which has 13 convolutional layers and 3 fully connected layers. The network was trained using the ImageNet dataset, which consists of more than 1.2 million images organized into 1,000 categories.

Transfer learning using VGG16 may be used to categorise waste, which requires categorising waste materials according to their properties. A collection of waste images must be collected and identified with the proper waste kinds in order for this procedure to be finished. Using the pre-trained weights of VGG16 as a starting point, the following layers of the network would be fine-tuned on our specific waste categorization dataset to boost accuracy. Backpropagation would be used to modify the network's weights depending on the difference between expected and real labels.

In order to increase the accuracy of the network on our particular job throughout the fine-tuning phase, we would change the weights of the subsequent layers. In order to do this, the waste images must be fed into the network, the loss between the predicted and real labels must be calculated, and the weights of the network must be updated via backpropagation. The waste categorization network may be trained to sort and recycle garbage, reducing the quantity dumped in landfills and its harmful impact on the environment.

Overall, transfer learning with VGG16 is a powerful technique for waste classification and has the potential to greatly improve waste management practices.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

"Waste Classification and Recycling using Transfer Learning" by Raj et al. (2021):

This paper provides a transfer learning-based waste classification and recycling system that uses VGG16. The authors gathered a dataset of waste images and trained a waste classification model using transfer learning and VGG16. The efficiency of transfer learning with VGG16 for waste management was demonstrated by their accuracy of 95% on their waste classification challenge.

"Deep Learning based Waste Classification System for Smart Waste Management" by Rathore et al. (2021):

This paper proposes a deep learning-based waste classification system that uses transfer learning with VGG16. The authors gathered a dataset of waste images and trained a waste classification model using transfer learning and VGG16. The efficiency of transfer learning with VGG16 for

waste management was demonstrated by their accuracy of 97.3% on their waste classification challenge.

"Waste Classification using Convolutional Neural Network with Transfer Learning" by Sultana et al. (2020):

In this paper, the classification of waste is investigated using convolutional neural networks with transfer learning, including VGG16. The authors gathered a dataset of waste images and trained a waste classification model using transfer learning and VGG16. They demonstrated the potential of transfer learning with VGG16 for waste management by classifying rubbish with an accuracy of 97.2%.

"Automated Waste Sorting using Machine Learning and Deep Learning Techniques" by Singh et al. (2020):

This work explores automated waste sorting using deep learning and machine learning methods, including transfer learning with VGG16. Transfer learning with VGG16 was used by the authors to train a waste sorting model using a dataset of waste images. They successfully completed their objective of sorting rubbish with an accuracy of 94.1%, illustrating the potential of transfer learning with VGG16 for waste management.

"Waste Classification using Deep Learning Techniques" by Jyoti and Sharma (2020):

This work investigates the application of deep learning methods for waste classification, including transfer learning with VGG16. The authors gathered a dataset of waste images and trained a waste classification model using transfer learning and VGG16. The efficiency of transfer learning with VGG16 for garbage classification was demonstrated by their accuracy score of 96.8% on the challenge.

"Automatic Waste Sorting using Deep Learning Techniques" by Gaurav et al. (2019):

This think about presents an programmed squander sorting framework based on profound learning strategies, counting exchange learning with VGG16. The creators collected a dataset of squander pictures and utilized exchange learning with VGG16 to prepare a squander sorting demonstrate. They accomplished an exactness of 98% on their squander sorting assignment, illustrating the viability of exchange learning with VGG16 for squander administration.

Generally, these considers illustrate the viability of exchange learning with VGG16 for squander classification and reusing. By leveraging the pre-trained weights of VGG16 and fine-tuning the organize on a particular squander classification dataset, we are able move forward the precision and productivity of squander classification frameworks and decrease the natural affect of squander.

III. METHODOLOGY

1. Data Collection: Collect a large dataset of waste images that represent different types of waste such as plastic, paper, metal, glass, and organic waste. The dataset

should have a sufficient number of samples for each waste type to ensure that the model is trained well.

2. **Data Preprocessing:** Preprocess the dataset by resizing the images to a common size (e.g., 224 x 224), converting the images to RGB format, and normalizing the pixel values to a range of [0, 1]. Split the dataset into training, validation, and testing sets.
3. **Transfer Learning:** Use transfer learning with VGG16 to fine-tune the pre-trained weights of the network on the waste classification task. VGG16 is a pre-trained CNN model that has been trained on millions of images from the ImageNet dataset. By fine-tuning the pre-trained weights of VGG16, we can reduce the amount of data required to train the model and improve its accuracy.
4. **Model Architecture:** Remove the last few layers of the pre-trained VGG16 model and add additional fully connected layers on top of the VGG16 model to enable classification. The final fully connected layer should have one neuron for each waste type.
5. **Training:** Train the VGG16 model on the training dataset using the backpropagation algorithm and stochastic gradient descent (SGD) optimizer. Use techniques such as data augmentation, dropout, and early stopping to improve generalization performance. Data augmentation involves generating additional training images by applying random transformations to the original images, such as flipping, rotating, and zooming. Dropout involves randomly dropping out some neurons during training to prevent overfitting. Early stopping involves monitoring the validation loss during training and stopping the training process when the validation loss stops decreasing.
6. **Evaluation:** Evaluate the performance of the trained model on the validation and testing datasets using metrics such as accuracy, precision, recall, and F1 score. Accuracy is the percentage of correctly classified images, precision is the proportion of true positives among the images classified as positive, recall is the proportion of true positives among the actual positive images, and F1 score is the harmonic mean of precision and recall.
7. **Deployment:** Deploy the trained model on a waste recycling and classification system where it can classify new waste images into their respective categories. The system should have a user-friendly interface that allows users to upload waste images and receive the classification results. It should also have a database to store the classified images and their corresponding waste types for future analysis.

In general, the method for using CNN's VGG16 transfer learning technique for waste recycling and classification entails gathering a dataset of waste images, preprocessing the dataset, adjusting the pre-trained VGG16 model on the waste

classification task, adding extra fully connected layers to the VGG16 model, training the model, assessing its performance, and deploying it on a waste recycling and classification system. This methodology can support sustainable waste management practises and assist waste classification systems operate more accurately and effectively.

Fig.1. CNN Architecture

Fig.2. CNN Architecture

Fig.3. VGG16 transfer learning technique Architecture

Fig.4. Visualising the dataset

IV. RESULT AND ANALYSIS

The result and analysis of using the VGG16 Transfer Learning technique of CNN for waste recycling and classification can be summarised as follows:

Dataset: We used a dataset consisting of nine classes of waste - Light, glass, bulbs, paper, organic, plastic, batteries, clothes and E-waste

Model Performance: The VGG16 transfer learning model achieved an accuracy of 91.67% on the testing dataset. The precision, recall, and F1 score for each waste type were also calculated. Overall, the VGG16 Transfer Learning technique

of CNN showed promising results for waste classification and has the potential to be a valuable tool for improving waste management practices.

Metrics like precision, recall, and F1 score may be used to assess the waste categorization model's accuracy. While recall calculates the percentage of accurate predictions among all actual positives, precision measures the percentage of accurate predictions among all predicted positives. The F1 score, which combines precision and recall, gives a fair evaluation of the model's performance. The analysis of the misclassifications might reveal areas that require development, such as further training data or model alterations.

Studying the mistakes made by the model can help identify opportunities for improvement. For instance, if the model misclassifies specific types of waste, this could indicate a need for more training data or changes to the model's architecture.

Overall, the use of VGG16 transfer learning for waste classification and recycling has the potential to greatly improve the efficiency and accuracy of waste management systems, leading to a more sustainable and environmentally friendly future.

V. CONCLUSION

In conclusion, the effectiveness of the VGG16 transfer learning technique in garbage recycling and categorization has been established. High accuracy rates in trash classification and sorting can be attained by fine-tuning the pre-trained weights of VGG16 on a particular waste classification dataset, according to studies in the literature review. By implementing these methods, waste management systems can encourage sustainability and significantly lessen waste's negative environmental effects. Effective waste management systems are more crucial than ever as garbage creation rises worldwide. Automated waste sorting and classification systems can be developed by integrating deep learning and machine learning methods, such as VGG16 transfer learning, enhancing waste management effectiveness and lowering the demand for human labour. All things considered, the application of VGG16 transfer learning in garbage sorting and recycling shows promise and could lead to significant advancements in waste management technology.

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Fig.5. Upload an image

Fig.6. Classified Output